

TEACHING SPEAKING: PROMOTING FLUENCY VIA MEANINGFUL CLASSROOM COMMUNICATION

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ABSTRACT

Speaking, as an important instrumental factor of English language learning and teaching, is "the process of building and sharing meaning through the use of verbal and non-verbal symbols, in a variety of contexts" (Chaney, 1998, p. 13). The ability to communicate in English smoothly and efficiently contributes to the success of the learners in every walk of life. That is the reason why the current global workplace requires classroom teachers to set the learning outcome as the achievement of fluency development in speaking. Rather than repeating of newly introduced forms or memorizing dialogues, providing a rich environment where meaningful communication takes place is more significant. This paper will examine fluency-related theoretical background in EFL teaching context before coming to the discussion of criteria for designing and selecting fluency activities, then propose several fluency-oriented activities which have been applied successfully in the context of communication classes in Can Tho City; those are appreciated by teachers as a means to nurture meaningful communication and increase student's willingness to speak.

1 INTRODUCTION

Improving students' English fluency in communication so as to make them more adaptable to modern society has always been a major concern for language teachers. Besides, speaking English fluently is often referred as an ultimate goal by learners; however, fluency in English speaking is not an objective that can be achieved easily by most learners of English. In reality, practicing oral fluency in the classroom can be challenging for various reasons including the lack of confidence, topic-related ideas and vocabulary, or worry of making mistakes. In my teaching context, the students are not willing to speak out their ideas; this fact could result from the lack of opportunities for interaction in the majority of Vietnamese EFL classes (Hiep, 2007; Canh, 2011; Ngan, 2013; Duy, 2014). Therefore, the goals of the paper is to introduce several fluency-building activities to teachers of English that could be used in their classrooms in order to stimulate meaningful classroom communication.

2 DISCUSSION

Fluency is a term often used in language teaching, but its definition varies based on specific contexts; hopefully, an investigation of its meaning would be beneficial when coming to the discussion of what constitutes effective fluency-oriented activities.

2.1 Fluency

Brumfit (1984) avers L2 fluency as “the maximally effective operation of the language system so far acquired by the student” (p. 42); Sajavaara (1987) claims the two aspects combined in L2 fluency are linguistic acceptability and smooth continuity of speech.

In the context of teaching English as a foreign language, Skehan’s notion of fluency related to “the learner’s capacity to produce language in real time without undue pausing or hesitation” (1996, p.22). Skehan (1996) emphasizes that fluency cannot be detached from meaning because it reflects the learner’s ability in dealing with real time communication. To Fillmore (1979, as cited in Nation, 1989, p. 377), a fluent speaker is aware of what and how to say without frequent pauses or hesitations. Riazantseva (2001) suggests that fluency has a link to the management of pausing and hesitation phenomena. Richards (2006) points out that fluency is the use of naturally occurring language when speakers involve and manage their speech in meaningful communication. Furthermore, Harmer (2015) points out that fluency means a focus on the content of speech to communicate as effectively as possible. For the purposes of this paper, fluency can be thought of as the command to speak naturally with minimum amount of pauses or hesitations in the target language and accurately enough to be understood.

2.2 Fluency-oriented approach

Under a focus on learner’s fluent speech, small grammatical or pronunciation mistakes are inessential, especially at the beginning of learning process. In fact, direct correction or heavy emphasis on those mistakes is considered harmful rather than helpful, since it may lead to undue monitor in learners’ mind, hindering natural acquisition of speaking ability (Ebsworth, 1998). The fluency-oriented approach believes that effective speaking ability is closely related to meaningful communication.

2.3 Accuracy-oriented approach

The approach that focus on repetition of newly introduced forms or grammatical correctness are considered as accuracy-oriented (Willerman, 2011). Although it used to be supported by many linguists, few EFL teachers favor this viewpoint these days due to the increase of speaking anxiety factors among students. Consequently, we see the necessity of combining certain language items into communication-oriented tasks.

2.4 What Constitute Effective Fluency-oriented Activities?

Fluency-building activities should be ‘open’ exercises encouraging the learners to be more creative and take risks with the language without worrying about ‘right’ or ‘wrong’ answer (Patterson, 2013). Teachers adopting this definition can focus more on natural production of language where open-ended activities modifying authentic situations are more appropriate.

Since fluency comes from being able to access that which one already knows (Nation, 2007, 6), a fluency-based activity should not emphasize too much new language forms, but instead allow the students multiple opportunities to activate and master the language they have already encountered while reducing unnatural hesitations.

During the fluency-boosting stage, it is better if prompting and correction are held back “as late as possible” so as not to interfere with the students’ opportunity to learn from negotiating with meaning (Lynch, 1997, p.324). Therefore, focus should be shifted onto the production of language and speed, rather than mistake correction. Moreover, it is crucial that achievable goals should be set in order to avoid inhibition in speech. Consequently, we see the necessity of combining certain achievable language items into communication-oriented tasks.

2.5 Sample Fluency-oriented Activities (Utilised at Nam Phuong Center for English)

The following activities are selected based on the mentioned-above criteria for fluency-building activities, as well as for their adaptability and appropriateness to the English teaching context in Mekong Delta, Viet Nam. Since the majority of learners from provinces of Mekong Delta are not willing to speak out and express their ideas in English language, the activities aim at stimulating natural classroom interaction while decreasing teacher’s focus on error corrections; as a result, students become more active and speak more fluent in English in spite of several insignificant mistakes. Moreover, it was suggested that the application and adaptation of effective fluency-oriented activities should focus on the following criteria:

1) Effective Communication

Communicating effectively means receiving and responding to right messages. To help the students more aware of this, teachers should encourage their students to feel the mood of the dialogue in any practice with fluency in the classroom.

2) Freer Practice

In order to reduce students’ speech inhibition, they should be given with opportunity to express themselves without worrying about being corrected by the teacher.

3) Useful Language

Teacher should offer visual supports like prompts of the target language or pictures which help students focus and remember language. Besides, students should be given an adequate amount of time to practice the language before they are ready to produce it in public.

4) Positive Signs of Comments

When giving feedback on a student's performance, teacher should show them several improved or developed points in their speech so as to motivate and encourage them, in case of there are mistakes, teacher can choose to talk about typical ones which are really harmful for their next performance.

Find Someone Who...

This activity is good as an icebreaker for first class introductions. It requires not much preparation except from a handout given to the students for them to record their answers.

1) Have the students walk around the room and talk to people they do not know well, following

the requirements from teacher such as “Find someone who has the first name “NGUYEN”, Find someone who do not come from Can Tho City”

2) Students ask different partners questions until they finish the requirements from teacher’s handout.

3) The student who finish first is the winner and will be invited to share his/her findings to the whole class.

Note: The teacher may wish to model the activity for the class first with a student volunteer.

This activity can be adapted into a wrap-up activity after the students already encountered the target structures; such as a use of present perfect tense in which students ask and answers questions like “Have you got a pet?”, “Have you ever visited another country?” This will give students opportunity to repeat the target structures several times without worrying about potential mistakes.

The Witness

This activity is suitable to wrap-up stage where students review and use the provided language into meaningful communication.

Prepare a series of 4 pictures of people which can be easily copied (for example: 4 men with beards or moustaches of differing ages).

Divide class into pairs (A and B). Student A is a witness and B is a policeman.

Pretend that student A witnessed a serious murder case, then this person need to provide the police information about the murderer.

Show all Student A's one of the pictures (Student B must not see it). Show it very briefly.

Student B must ask the witness to describe the person he/she saw. Student B can ask questions for details: hair, age, clothes, height, and weight. Student B should take notes while student A provides information.

Now give the Policemen (student B) the lineup of 4 people. Which one did the witness describe?

A Debate

1) Consider these things carefully before the lesson starts:

Topic: It’s important that you choose the topic carefully, choose something that students can relate to, something they will be interested in and want to talk about, such as a ban of using mobile phones in school campus.

How do you want the students to debate?

- All class or in small groups?
- Who will control the debate?

- Some people who judge who wins?

2) Let students brainstorm on points for and against the debate motion.

3) Introduce the useful language in order to help them express those views coherently in English, those pieces of structures could be: “I strongly agree...”, “I am of the point that...”, “I have another view...”

4) Practice

The people involved in the debate have enough time to practice what they want to say.

The teacher doesn't influence the debate. Let the students influence the flow of the content.

The teacher can assign some students in the audience a helpful task like looking at the verbal and non-verbal language of their friends.

3 CONCLUSION

This paper has provide a discussion on the topic of fluency by examining different points of view and offering a brief outline of several fluency-oriented activities for teachers of English language to adapt to suit the needs and abilities of their students, as well as their own teaching styles. Moreover, the following factors should be taken into account in choosing and adapting fluency-oriented activities like effective communication, freer practice, useful language, and positive signs of comments from English language teachers.

The teachers at Nam Phuong Center for English and I implemented those activities in several classes with learners at different levels of English language proficiency. Significant improvements in students' spoken fluency were observed and admitted by teachers in classes where the activities was introduced and conducted on a regular basis, with a variety of topics. Besides, the activities also has obvious merits of enhancing classroom atmosphere, stimulating students' willingness to speak English with their partners. In spite of the fact that the benefits of those activities are limited in my own teaching context and experience, I hope that this article will be helpful to other teachers in Viet Nam in general and in Mekong Delta in specific who are keen on investigating and experiencing new techniques for improving their students' fluency in speaking.

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